

The Cycles of AI Winters: A Historical Analysis and Modern Perspective

Imagine a garden with seasons - time of quick growth to time to sleep. Just as the field of artificial intelligence has gone through cycles throughout its own history, we have periods where promise and progress are extraordinary and funding increases, and then other periods where disappointment and reduced funding occur. These downturns are known as "AI winters," a term that perfectly captures the chilling effect on research, development, and investment in artificial intelligence technologies.

Understanding AI Winters

An AI winter is when the enthusiasm and inevitable support for artificial intelligence research and development cool over and freeze over. It is almost like a new startup shuts down because investors lose confidence, and the technology has not changed at all.

Historical Context and Major AI Winters

The First AI Winter (1974-1980)

The first significant AI winter emerged from what we might call "oversized expectations" (McCarthy et al., 1955). Imagine that child who thinks they can build a skyscraper with wooden blocks; that ambition is great, but the tools and understanding are not ready. Just as early AI researchers made big promises about machine translation and general problem solving that could not be met with the technology of the day.

The ALPAC (Automatic Language Processing Advisory Committee) report of 1966 was one of the principal catalysts for the setting into motion that winter. Think of a hard working promising athlete who, after so much training, was not able to qualify for a major competition. Similarly, the ALPAC report (Committee, 1966) crashed expectations about machine translation with findings that, despite millions of dollars in funding, automated translation systems were no better than human translators and much costlier.

A lot of this winter was due to the limitations of the perceptron, an early neural network model. Marvin Minsky and Seymour Papert's 1969 book "Perceptrons" demonstrated fundamental limitations of single-layer neural networks, much like showing that a car, no matter how well-engineered, cannot fly. That is, their mathematical proof that perceptrons could not solve simple problems such as determining whether a given line drawing was connected or disconnected struck a deadly blow to the research in neural networks (Minsky and Papert, 1969).

Particularly damning of AI's promises versus its results was a 1972 report for the British government, the so-called Lighthill Report. Sir James Lighthill divided AI research into three categories:

1. Successful Advanced Automation
2. Computer Based Research in Central Nervous System Function (worthwhile)
3. Bridge Building Research (to bridge the gap between the first two categories, but seemingly unsuccessful).

Think of this categorization as similar to evaluating a new medicine: While some middle steps (such as basic research and particular applications) may appear promising, translating laboratory findings into practical treatments generally does not work. Criticism like that from a respected figure outside the AI field—particularly when, as in this case, they were someone who was not an expert on AI—was very damaging, like a neutral referee at a game calling out obvious problems like players not knowing where the ball was (Lighthill, 1972).

The consequences were massive and enormous. However, research funding was drastically reduced, from DARPA in the United States, in particular. Consider a garden where water supply is disallowed – yes, some plants may survive, but overall growth slows to a crawl. Just like before, many AI research programs were either ended or scaled back considerably.

This period also saw the collapse of several key research directions:

- It was majorly scaled back for Natural Language Processing projects.
- Funding cuts forced Computer Vision research to grind to a halt.
- After all, General Problem Solving programmes, that could have been the key for artificial general intelligence were largely abandoned.

It did not end in academia. As a financial crisis hits both the banks and their customers, so the AI winter also affected both researchers and industries embracing AI technologies. Companies that had invested in AI research began to rebrand their work with less ambitious terms like "expert systems" and "pattern recognition" to distance themselves from the increasingly stigmatized field of artificial intelligence.

The Second AI Winter (1987-1993)

After specialised AI hardware markets collapsed, particularly Lisp machines, there was the second major AI winter. For instance, imagine spending a lot on specialised typewriters while personal computers were becoming commonplace; this is kind of what happened when general purpose computers became potent enough to run AI programs, which made expensive specialised hardware useless (Hendler, 2008).

The Rise and Fall of Lisp Machines

Especially in the case of the Lisp machine story, it is illustrative of this period. These machines are like professional grade cameras, very powerful but also very expensive. These specialised computers optimised for AI programming in Lisp were developed very heavily: Symbolics, Lisp Machines Inc., and Texas Instruments invested heavily in them (Steele & Gabriel, 1993).

But, just as digital cameras became the end for many specialised photography tools, it was the rapid development of the general purpose computer that doomed Lisp machines. At the same time, workstations from the likes of Sun Microsystems and the rising power of personal computers made specialised AI hardware with price tags of \$100,000 or more unworthy of its price (Campbell-Kelly et al., 2018).

The Expert Systems Crisis

This period was also characterised by the downfall of expert systems. AI programs were created, which were called expert systems, to replicate the ability of experts to make decisions. Imagine trying to capture all the knowledge of an experienced doctor in a book of rules - this was essentially what expert systems attempted to do.

Initially, expert systems showed great promise:

- In the early 1980s, for example, XCON for Digital Equipment Corporation, saved the company an estimated \$40 million annually.
- Chemical analysis was successfully deployed in numerous laboratories with DENDRAL.
- Per example, MYCIN, designed for diagnosing blood infections, sometimes beats human doctors.

However, several fundamental problems emerged (Hayes-Roth et al., 1983):

1. **Brittleness:** Expert systems could not solve situations outside the programmed rules. Rather than finding an alternative route, it is like a GPS system failing completely when it encounters a road it was not expecting.
2. **Knowledge Acquisition Bottleneck:** Transferring that human expertise into rule based systems was very time consuming and expensive. Imagine trying to include in writing everything that an experienced chef knows about cooking with regards to their art: not how to do things, but how to do them, why they do it, and when to do it.
3. **Maintenance Nightmare:** Updating these systems was complicated indeed. When adding new rules, there were always unexpected interactions between old rules, just as changing a single ingredient in a complicated recipe alters the whole dish.

The Market Collapse

By the late 1980s, several factors converged to create a perfect storm:

1. **Hardware Market Transformation:** In the wake of the collapse of the specialised AI hardware market, many companies struggled. In 1991, Symbolics, a pioneer of sprocketing, went bankrupt (Newquist, 1994).
2. **Funding Cuts:** Just as the first AI winter was brought on by government funding cuts, the second winter was due to corporate funding drying up. Then companies that had spent millions helping to develop AI research and development started to doubt where their return on investment was.
3. **Strategic Defense Initiative Impact:** The Strategic Defense Initiative (SDI, or "Star Wars" program) had provided significant funding for AI research. Its secondary components—its AI components—were scaled back, and that ripple effect carried through the field (Roland & Shiman, 2002).

Industry Response

The industry's response to this winter was particularly interesting:

1. **Rebranding:** Companies began avoiding the term "artificial intelligence," instead using terms like "advanced computing" or "knowledge-based systems."
2. **Shift in Focus:** Research shifted towards more specific, achievable goals rather than grand visions of human like AI.
3. **Integration:** Rather than trying to sell its AI techniques as products, they started to be integrated into conventional softwares.

Academic Impact

The academic world also felt the effects:

- Many AI programs were scaled back across many universities.
- There was more directed research funding for applications than for general AI.
- While the field started to split into more and more specialised subfields such as machine learning, natural language processing, and computer vision.

Despite this fragmentation, it was also a good thing, since it forced researchers to move away from general artificial intelligence towards more concrete, achievable goals (McDermott, 1987).

Modern Parallels and Differences

AI today is vastly different than past, yet also quite similar. Modern deep learning systems, while incredibly powerful, still face challenges that echo past concerns:

1. **Explainability Issues:** Like black box expert systems of the past, many modern AI systems are making decisions that are hard to understand or explain (LeCun et al., 2015).
2. **Resource Requirements:** Modern AI essentially mirrors these lisp machine characteristics: they were expensive and specialised hardware. And modern AI often requires a lot of computing power and energy use.
3. **Data Dependency:** Just like the early systems, which were not equipped to handle the realities of the world appropriately, today's AI system often calls for large quantities of clean and high quality training data.

But their differences are highlighted. Practically successful AI systems today have gained economic value in a slew of applications, from image recognition to language processing. It also offers a buffer against the kind of complete industry collapse seen in previous winters.

Preventing Future Winters

To avoid another AI winter, the field must address several critical factors:

Expectation Management

Just like a good teacher can challenge students without being overwhelming, the AI community must strike the balance between what it aspires to and what is functionally possible. Part of this is being clear on either the strengths and limitations of AI systems.

Technical Robustness

AI systems, like a home, need to be built with robustness and reliability. One part covers biases, safety, and system stability along with other topics.

Sustainable Development

As opposed to pursuing quick advances at all costs, the field ought to centre around sustainable progress. This means developing systems that are:

- Energy efficient
- Economically viable
- Ethically sound

- Technically maintainable

Conclusion

Artificial intelligence winters teach us very good things about the importance of balanced progress in artificial intelligence. We, like a farmer, who has to prioritise getting immediate yields but at the same time looking after his soil health long term, have to balance rapid development with sustainable development.

The crux is not avoiding ambitious goals but rather taking our ambitions seriously and doing them with scientific rigour, ethical care, and practical implementation. If we can keep the public informed about AI's skills and deficiencies, prioritise robust and sustainable development, and provide real world value from future AI advances, we can lock the winter off the bat.

Though we continue to progress, it is important to keep in perspective that these setbacks serve as nothing more than indicators of what is next rather than a harbinger of that dreaded time of year. Today's global future of AI is not about unbridled optimism or excessive caution but a realistic, evidence based, constructively cautious development and deployment.

Boldly go where no human or AI has gone before!
Ferhat Sarikaya

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